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Molecular diversity in cyclization of Ugi-products leading to the synthesis of 2,5-diketopiperazines: computational study

Vahideh Zadsirjan¹, [Morteza Shiri](#)¹, Majid M. Heravi¹, Tayebeh Hosseinnejad¹,
Suhas A. Shintre², Neil A. Koorbanally²

1 Department of Chemistry, Alzahra University, Vanak, Tehran 1993893973, Iran.

2 School of Chemistry and Physics, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Private Bag X54001, Durban 4000, South Africa.

Abstract

Ugi-adducts were obtained via a one-pot four-component reaction of divergent aldehydes, amines, aroylacrylic acids and isocyanide in methanol. These products were subjected to intramolecular Michael addition in the presence of K₂CO₃ in DMF at room temperature to afford a single product. Literally, the formation of two heterocyclic systems, 6-membered diones or 7-membered diones are possible, which could not be identified by conventional spectroscopic methods. The X-ray crystallographical data was obtained for one selected product, which indicated preferential formation of the corresponding 6-membered dione. In order to establish the generality of this mode of cyclization, the quantum chemistry calculations were performed. The obtained results confirmed the favorable formation of 6-membered diones in the gas and also several solution phases. All the products were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities.

Graphical Abstract

Keywords: Ugi reaction, Aroylacrylic acids, Base catalysis, Intramolecular Michael addition, 2,5-Diketopiperazines, Molecular diversity, Density functional theory, Quantum theory of atoms in molecules, Polarized continuum model, Antibacterial and antifungal activities.